

THE DIFFICULTIES OF TEACHING SPEAKING IN ENGLISH IN MEDICAL INSTITUTIONS

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ABSTRACT

The article discusses the importance of the right approach in teaching English to medical students, for whom English is not a major subject, but is important for their future profession. Problems such as low motivation and poor English proficiency are discussed. Examples of solutions to these problems using various methods of teaching English are given.

There is no doubt that English has become a universal language.

Today English is used as a first or second language by at least one billion people worldwide. That is why it is very important for me to be a professional teacher with modern methods of teaching English as a foreign language. No one can ignore the need and value of methods of teaching English as a foreign or second language. The needs of students vary. Some students learn visually, some learn orally, some have short attention spans, and all come from different backgrounds. To meet the needs of all students, different methods must be used. Some of these methods are used with a variety of resources, while others are developed independently by teachers based on their experience teaching in a medical setting. Teaching English as a foreign language is especially important in developing countries where English is considered a foreign language. Obviously, people want better opportunities, which can only be obtained with a good command of English.

English language teaching in health care organizations is based on clear specific goals: communicative behavior in professional settings and possible budget situations (hospitals, clinics, pharmacies), goal-oriented, English language teaching is based on a professionally oriented, interdisciplinary, communicative-activist approach, Thus, the implementation of a professionally oriented competency-based educational process has been achieved.

It is very important for teachers because we usually learn our native language by first hearing or listening to others speak, hearing good spoken English as you understand it, you will improve all aspects of your speech. If you can understand movies and shows in English, try listening to news and documentary programs as well. An easier way to practice is to listen to English learning CDs, MP3s or computer programs at home or in a language class at school. You can also find English-language radio, television, and study materials on the Internet. In today's society, there are many more opportunities for language enrichment. Modern

listening instruction Effective, modern listening instruction includes everything from interactive exercises to multimedia resources. Listening skills are best taught through simple, straightforward exercises that focus on the learning process rather than the end product. Whether you are working with a large or small group of students, you can use any of the examples below to develop your own methods for teaching students how to listen, write, read, and speak.

Speaking is one of the major speech activities. Students exchange information through speaking. Speaking plays an important role in learning English. Without speaking, communication would not be possible. Speaking accounts for 30% of speech. Speaking is the best means of importing and consolidating elementary linguistic knowledge of the English language, assimilating, developing habits and building skills. Higher education students will be able to use English units, expressions, words, phrases, and sentences in speech. Positive and sustained fading. A program of learning to speak English as a foreign language is clearly impossible without a gradual assimilation of English phonological vocabulary and grammatical material.

Speaking instruction should preferably begin in the first lesson. Teaching speaking is closely related to other phonological activities such as listening, reading, and writing.

In my survey of medical students, I identified the following reasons for the decreased motivation of medical students to learn English: "Students' motivation to learn English was decreased because they could not speak English." Quite a few reasons were identified to explain this phenomenon:

- There is a shortage of English language teachers in both urban and rural schools, resulting in a persistent lack of teachers in schools or a complete lack of foreign language instruction;
- Has a low or basic level of knowledge obtained during the study of a foreign language at school; - Has a low level of knowledge in the subject at school; - Has a low level of knowledge in the subject at school; - Has a low level of knowledge in the subject at school
- Has an unfriendly relationship with the teacher who teaches the subject;
- Have little understanding of the need to use English in real life. However, some students assume to communicate in the target language when going abroad for the purpose of tourism, visiting relatives, etc.
- difficulties with the perception and memorization of a large amount of text material; - monotonous method of teaching the discipline;
- the complexity of teaching English, as a result of the lack of interest in the classroom; - lack of ability to learn English, it is difficult given;
- Language barrier, lack of voice and fear of making a mistake;

Learning to speak has a mechanism. Without this mechanism, speaking cannot be taught, organized, or taught. It is pronunciation, sound combinations, words, phrases, sentences, intonation, accentuation, tuning, and questions. Teachers must teach them in advance. Students must pronounce them correctly. When students are able to use them, they will focus only on what is being said. Teaching Comet helps teachers find and choose simple and effective methods and exercises to teach speaking.

These include:

1. The linguistic features, difficulties of teaching speaking.

- a) correctly selected the language materials of speaking such as phonetics, lexis, grammar.
- b) features, difficulties of selected phonetic lexic, grammar materials of speaking in the forms, in the meanings, in the usages.
- c) difficulties in correct by pronouncing, in the intonation, in the stress.
- d) difficulties in the skills and habits of correctly using sentences. e) Using replica.

2. Linguistic features and difficulties in teaching speaking.

- a) Addressing someone or something.
- b) Speaking in situations.
- c) Using aids and equipment to teach speaking.
- d) Motivations for teaching speaking.
- e) Conditions for teaching speaking.

3. The psychology features, difficulties of teaching speaking

- a) being, using the stimulus for teaching speaking;
- b) being, having needs for teaching speaking;
- c) expressing orally minds;
- d) memories and etc.

Listening and speaking together form oral speech, which is oral speech communication. Without listening, speaking is not possible. Listening and receiving information allows students to give answers in speaking. Listening comprehension provides students with the vocabulary, phrases, sentences, and their pronunciation necessary for speaking. Speaking is also related to reading. Reading gives students new information and content. They then use that information in their speech. Reading also helps students consolidate and master the pronunciation of words, phrases, and intonation. To do this, it is necessary to help teach speaking. Speaking is also closely related to writing.

Writing helps students remember information from spoken language.

In other words, speaking can help develop listening, reading, and writing skills. The connection between these language activities is very important for teaching, learning, and learning speaking.

Listening, speaking, reading, and writing complement each other when teaching English. Speaking can be divided into monologic, interactive, and polylogic speech. Monologic and dialogic speech are taught in schools, high schools and colleges. However, polylogical speech is not taught there.

Teaching speaking has its own goals, content, mechanisms, and methodological techniques. Teaching speaking has a purpose. Teaching speaking in English has its own goals.

The first goal: to teach speaking as a means of teaching English or as a means of communicating in English.

A secondary goal: to be able to use speaking to build communication and speaking skills.

In practice, students actively participate in discussions on topics that are relevant to them, such as "modern human problems," "healthy living," and "modern English."

Conclusion. In short, speaking becomes a means of communicating in English, and speaking itself can be taught through the process of speaking. Speaking should be taught so that it can be used in activities. Teachers must develop habits of speaking. Develop the habit of using speaking in speech activities. Program requirements Speaking instruction must be

conducted and organized according to program requirements. Each institution, school, lyceum, or college has its own program and its own requirements for teaching speaking. These requirements for speaking instruction are written into the curriculum. Teachers must understand them and teach speaking in accordance with them.

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